

A Review on Identification of Factors Causing Delay in Metro Rail Project

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Abstract : One of the main problems the construction sector is dealing with is construction delays. From a few days to years, delay issues can have different effects on a project depending on their features. In building projects, they have a major financial, environmental, and social impact. India's fast urbanization necessitates the development of urban metro rail projects and other transportation options. Nevertheless, a number of metro projects that are being built in Indian cities are beset by a number of problems that impair project cost, schedule, and construction quality. In a similar vein, the top three most important causes of cost overruns are: changes in government policies, laws, or the project's timeline, which results in increased costs; and force majeure. Mitigating these risks through proper life cycle contract management and risk allocation would facilitate timely completion of the metro projects with justified value for money to the government.

Keywords : Urban Metro Rail projects; Time Overrun; Cost Overrun;

1. INTRODUCTION

Construction delay is a foremost problem facing the construction industry in almost all countries in the world. Delays occur in almost every construction project and their magnitudes vary considerably from project to project, ranging from a few days to years. It is generally understood that construction delay is the most critical factor affecting the delivery of construction projects in terms of time, budget and the required quality [17]. However, it is very important to identify the exact causes and their significance in order to minimise and avoid the impact of delays in construction projects. Construction projects completed on time were a signal of project efficiency [18]; however, construction processes depend on a number of unpredictable factors that occur from various sources. These sources include the performance of construction stakeholders, availability of resources, site conditions, contract types, weather conditions and the contractual relations between stakeholders. However, it rarely happens that a project is completed within the specified time and budget. In this context, this research study focuses on analysing and quantifying the impact of delay factors in a Railway construction project (Track doubling).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There is substantial literature available corresponding to delay in construction projects ranging from case examples of developing to developed nations. A majority of researches focus on the identification of critical factors and impacts of delay specific to a region. This study takes reference of the above mentioned category of works to derive a methodology for research.

Assaf & Al-Hejji (2006) examined the construction projects in Saudi Arabia using a questionnaire based study and the findings reported that 70 % of the considered construction projects failed to complete within the stipulated time. The most common factor responsible for the delay as identified by the owner, consultant and the contractor using questionnaire survey was "Change Order". In a study based in Nigeria, Ajanlekoko (1987) observed the schedule compliance in construction projects to be poor. Ogunlana, Promkuntong & Jearkjirm (1996) observed significant delays in Thailand whereas Al-Momani (2000) conducted an investigation of severe construction delays in Jordan.

Ahmed et al. (2003) emphasized on the need to identify the causes of delay in construction industry in Florida and advocated that the delays could be mitigated by working on the identified causes. Alaghbari et al. (2007) reported the factors of delay in building construction projects in Malaysia by conducting an opinion survey on shortlisted 31 factors. This study measured the importance of factors classified in four categories –contractor factors, owner

factors, consultant factors and external factors. Mezher & Tawil (1998) reported the important factors of delay in the study conducted for construction projects in Lebanon. Financial issues in case of owner, contractual relationships for a contractor and project management issues for consultant were identified as the most important factors of delay.

Sambasivan & Soon (2007) studied the factors of project delay and its repercussions on project completion in the Malaysian construction industry. The ten most significant causes of delay identified from a set of twenty eight different causes were (1) contractor's improper planning, (2) contractor's poor site management, (3) inadequate contractor experience, (4) inadequate client's finance and payments for completed work, (5) problems with subcontractors, (6) shortage in material, (7) labor supply, (8) equipment availability and failure, (9) lack of communication between parties, and (10) mistakes during the construction stage. Memon et al. (2014) studied the factors of time overrun in case of Malaysian construction industry and reported that frequent design changes; change in the scope of the project; financial difficulties of owner; delays in decision making; and unforeseen ground conditions as the most contributing factors.

Al-Khalil & Al-Ghafly (1999) determined the most important causes of delay in public utility projects in Saudi Arabia. The three parties i.e. Contractors, Consultants and Owners, were found to agree on the importance ranking of delay causes. Koushki, Al-Rashid & Kartam (2005) derived the three main causes of time-delays included changing orders, owners' financial constraints and owners' lack of experience in the construction projects in Kuwait. The findings of the study by Faridi & El-Sayegh (2006) mention that half of the construction projects face delays because of approval in construction drawings from authorities, poor pre-planning and slow decision making process. Al-Momani (2000) found out the major factors of delay as – poor design, harsh weather, changes in design, unforeseen site conditions, and late delivery. An investigation and interpretation of the findings from the mentioned set of studies in the Middle East region reveal that approval, scope change and poor project delivery (slow decision making) are the common factors affecting the project schedule performance.

Iyer & Jha (2006) investigated the factors affecting the project performance in the construction sector of India. The study revealed that 40% of the construction projects are experiencing schedule overruns. The outcome was based on a questionnaire survey of 55 shortlisted attributes followed by factor analysis of the data to derive the critical success and failure factors. The identified list of seven critical failure factors affecting the schedule performance comprise of - conflict among project participant, project manager's ignorance, hostile socioeconomic environment, owner's incompetence, the indecisiveness of project participants, harsh climatic condition at the site and project specific factor. Desai & Bhatt (2013) studied the critical causes of delay in Indian residential construction projects. The study accounted the most significant factors as- original contract duration was too short; legal disputes between various parties; ineffective delay penalties; delay in progress payments by the owner; and delay to furnish and deliver the site to the contractor by the owner.

Frimpong, Oluwoye & Crawford (2003) used the relative importance weight method to derive the relative importance of factors causing delay. Sambasivan & Soon (2007) calculated the relative importance index (RII) of the factors of the overall dataset and within various groups of responses. The index was used in the ranking of factors and comparison of the relative importance of the factors as perceived by the three groups of respondents i.e. clients, contractor and consultants. Alaghbari et al. (2007) used the mean score for ranking of factors causing delay. Chan and Kumaraswamy (1997) analysed and ranked the factors of time overruns in Hong Kong construction projects using RII. The research also compared the differing perceptions of delay factors with the outcome of similar studies in Saudi Arabia and Nigeria. Kaliba, Muya & Mumba (2009) worked out the causes of schedule delays and cost overruns in road construction projects in Zambia using RII. A questionnaire survey based study by Doloi et al. (2012) identified the key factors affecting delay in the Indian construction industry using RII. Assaf, Al-Khalil & Al-Hazmi (1995) categorised causes of delay in 9 groups and calculated their relative importance by conducting a survey. The study revealed that the contractor, owner and architects have a coherence in the ranking of individual delay factors. Whereas there existed a difference in opinion for ranking of groups of delay factors. Alinaitwe, Apolot & Tindiwensi (2013) studied the causes of time and cost performance in Uganda's public sector construction projects. The major identified causes of delay were- Change of work scope and/or changes in material specifications; High inflation, insurance and interest rates; Poor monitoring and control, due to incompetent and/or unreliable supervisors; Delayed payment to contractors, subcontractors and/or suppliers; and Fuel shortages. The study comprised of computation of frequency index, severity index and importance index followed by ranking of factors. The results were validated on a case study of civil aviation projects.

3. CAUSES OF DELAYS

Researchers have interested in inspecting many causes of delay in construction industries. Odeh and Battaineh [3] study in Jordan stated that contractor's financial problems, change of order, and poor planning – scheduling of the project are the major causes of delay. Majid and McCaffer [4] also indicated the major causes of delays, effects of delays, and methods of reducing construction project delays in Aceh, Indonesia. A total of fifty-seven delay factors are recognized and grouped into eight; contractor-related delays; equipment-related delays; client-related delays; material-related delays; finance-related delays; consultant-related delays; external-related delays; and manpower-related delays. The results also showed that time overrun and cost overrun were the most common effects.

A case study research in Egypt listed eighty-four delay factors that classified into nine major groups; materials, financing, project changes, contractual relationships, rules and regulations, manpower, scheduling and control, equipment, and environmental factors [5]. Long [6] also compiled effects of delay in construction project and mentioned increased material handling, loss of productivity, and additional mobilization as some of the causes.

4. TYPES OF CONSTRUCTION DELAY

In order to identify the delay responsibility among parties, the practitioners must determine whether the delay is critical or noncritical. Schedule delays can be organized in several ways. Braimah [7] as shown at figure 1, presented basic delay classification based on responsibility, excusability/compensability, and timing. Based on responsibility, owner-caused delays, contractor-caused delays, and third party are included. Concurrent delay and non-concurrent delay are listed under the timing-based delay. While excusable non-compensable and excusable non-compensable and non-excusable delays are listed under excusability/compensability.

Figure 1. Classification of Project Delays [7]

a. Excusable and Non-Excusable Delays

In definition, excusable delay can be described as a delay caused by unforeseeable event beyond the control of construction project parties. Furthermore, excusable delay is categorized into two; Excusable Non-Compensable delays and Excusable Compensable delays.

i. Excusable Non-Compensable Delays (EN)

These delays are caused by many factors beyond control of the contractor, owner or other construction parties. Acts of God, force majeure, unforeseen underground site conditions, and labor – material shortages beyond expectations of construction parties at the time of contract agreement are examples of this type of delay [8, 9]. In this condition, the contractor is allowed to extend the construction time period (EOT) without any delay liquidated damages.

ii. Excusable-Compensable Delays (EC)

Excusable-compensable delays are caused by owner or his/her representatives. These delays are including caused

by site access failure preparing, variation/change orders, differing site conditions and/or incomplete drawings and specifications [10]. Due to these delays, the owner entitles the contractor a time extension (EOT) and financial damages. However, if a “no-damage-for-delay” clause written in contract form, a probable determination of compensability can be seriously challenged. The identification of which delays are owner’s responsibility counts significantly upon the contract language itself [11].

iii. *Non-Excusable Delays (NE)*

The contractor or its subcontractors’ fault and negligence are causing this type of delays. The consequence of these delays is the contractor has to be liable to any damages to owner according to the contract agreement. The examples of these causes of delays are insufficient manpower, lack of resources, material distribution problems, equipment-related delays, financial problems and etc.

b. *Critical and Non-Critical Delays*

Critical path is known as the longest distance of the project start date and finish date. If a delay occurs in activities of critical path, it obviously affects the project completion date. Some projects might be have more than one critical path(s) and it leads into a dispute over the occurred delays. However, non- critical delays do not affect the project completion date but it has to be noticed that a delay near critical path can affect the completion date if it consumes out of the available float.

c. *Concurrent Delays*

Concurrent delays are widely known as two or more delays caused by different parties at the same time which can affect the project completion date. Arditi and Robinson [10] explained that two or more delays occur concurrently and caused extension time in the overall project, must be occurring in the same time period and must be able to affect the overall project duration independently of each other. Concurrent delay is the most challengeable type of delay because both parties will use this delay to against the other party. Owners will use this delay to collect liquidated damages while contractors will use it to waive their inexcusable delays and avoid damages entitlements [8]. In terms of definitions and apportionment of concurrent delays, the practitioners, researchers, and court law are generally inconsistent [12].

Kraiem and Diekmann [13] proposed different rules which shall be called as “Easy Rule” and ‘Fair Rule”. The difference of those rules is lie on the apportioning of liquidated damages. In “Easy Rule”, liquidated damages apportionment is not accepted, instead, the contractor is allowed to have an extension of time and each party suffering its own losses. Table 1 shows the summarize of remedies from concurrent delays.

Table 1. Remedies for Concurrent delays [13]

Concurrent delay type	Remedy (for critical path)	
Any delay concurrent with excusable non-compensable	Time extension	
Excusable compensable concurrent with non-excusable non-compensable	Easy rule	Fair rule
	Time extension	Appointment

5. SCHEDULE DELAYS ANALYSIS

a. *Schedule Delay Analysis Methods*

Different types of delays can be occurred in construction project and involving more than one party. In other that, some methods have been developed for analyzing the impact of the delays and identifying the project party liabilities. Yang and Kao [14] explained that the ideal methods should perform a fair and accurate delay analysis results and can be accepted by contract participants and professional schedule analyst.

i. *As-planned vs. As-Built Method*

This method compares the finish date of two schedules, as-planned and as-built. The obtained different numbers will be noted as delay days of the construction project. Ndekugri, Braimah [15] stated that this method is inexpensive, simple and easy to understand but it hard to identify changes in critical path and unable to managing complex construction delays.

ii. *Impacted As-Planned Method*

This method starts with as-planned schedule and applied by inserting the delays. If the owners are willing to obtain the contractor-caused delay, they can insert numbers of contractor delay to the as-planned schedule. It also applies to the contractor that submit extension time of the project claim by adding the delay caused by owners to the as-planned schedule in appropriate sequence [16].

iii. *The Collapsed As-Built Method*

As-built schedule is used as the baseline schedule of this method and applied twice both from owner's viewpoint and contractor's. From contractor's viewpoint, the delay caused by owner will be eliminated from as-built schedule and the given numbers of compared it to as-built schedule will be the liability of owner. From the owner and third party, the implementation is vice versa [17]. This method is commonly used but still have some disadvantages such as concurrent delays unable to be recognized and dynamic nature of project's critical paths are not considered [18].

iv. *Isolated Delay Type Technique*

This technique divides the project durations in as-planned schedule into several scenarios and applied based on the owner's and contractor's viewpoint. It examines delay-caused by contractor and ignore other delays caused by owner or third party when analyzing based on contractor's viewpoint [19].

v. *Window But-For Technique*

The owner's and contractor's viewpoint are used continuously in divided as-planned project duration scenarios. The delay caused from owner will be inserted into first scenario and the result schedule will be the new baseline. Further, the contractor-caused delay will be inserted into that new baseline and it completes the analyzing of first scenario. The result date of first scenario later becomes a new baseline of second scenario and the same analyzing will be implemented. The details of this methods process will be found elsewhere [20].

vi. *Isolated Collapsed But-For Method (ICBF)*

Starting with as-built schedule, this method divides the project duration into scenarios. One scenario consists of all delay types and the delay will be eliminated according to the types and viewpoints. This method considers the viewpoint of owner and contractor continuously in each scenario. Further, Yang and Yin [21] explained the detail process information of this method.

vii. *Effect-based Delay Analysis Method (EDAM)*

This method proposed by Yang and Kao [22] based on study problems of windows-based delay analysis methods. EDAM conducts delay analysis using extracted windows and delay impacts based on the delay effects on critical path. The main advantage of this method is the ability to clearly allocate liability of each party in order to solve concurrent delays problems.

b. *Comparison Result*

Kamandang, Yang [23] examined seven schedule delay analysis methods above and stated that the most suitable schedule delay methods must be able to solve concurrent delay and allocate the project parties' liability. According to the previous research [23], methods that divide project schedule into scenarios and consider owner's and contractor's viewpoint continuously produce the most stable and accurate results. In order to calculate the allocation of each party's schedule delays liability, the equations are needed as presented in the EDAM [22]. However, the clear words in contract agreement discussed concurrent delay liability are highly recommended to solve disputes that might be coming along the delays.

6. CONCLUSION

Optimum utilization and timely completion ascertain the financial and economic sustainability of metro rail projects. Delays and shortfall of demand cause a threat to the viability of these projects. Metro rail projects in India are commonly characterized by delay in completion and shortfall in demand. Various studies refer to risk assessment and suggest risk mitigation strategies in different sectors of infrastructure construction projects. Even though there is a common occurrence of delay and demand shortfall in metro rail projects, still, evidence in the form of established literature addressing the issues in urban rail sector are very limited. This paper establishes the need to study the causes of delay and demand shortfall in metro rail projects. It also proposes to investigate the inter-relationship between the factors contributing to delay and demand shortfall in similar infrastructure projects.

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